

AXIOMATIC DEFINITION OF COMPLEX PROBABILITY

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we set up the base of the complex probability theory. The following concepts are defined: the axiomatic definition of complex probability; the conditional complex probability; discrete and continuous complex random variables; some distributions of complex random variables. We obtain the addition formula, the multiplication formula, the formula of total probability and the Bayes' formula for complex probability.

1. INTRODUCTION

The modern axiomatics of real probability theory was invented by A.N. Kolmogorov in 1933 [1]. The complex probability is the natural development of real probability. In probability theory, the conditional probability $P(A|B)$ is the probability of a present event A to occur under the condition that a past event B has occurred; $P(A)$ is the probability of a present event A to occur. If we want to consider the potential influence of probability on future events, what kind of probability do we need? Based on the computer simulation of the probability and some other facts, I find we require the complex probability. Real part of the complex probability determines the possibility of an event at the present time, and people doesn't feel the imaginary part of complex probability at the present time, but the imaginary part will have an influence on probability of the following event. In this paper, we mainly give axiomatic definition of complex probability and some properties of it. This theory is the foundations for applications of the complex probability. The present paper only discusses theoretical problems of the complex probability and the applications will be discussed in some other papers.

2. AXIOMATIC DEFINITION OF COMPLEX PROBABILITY

We denote by Ω a sample space. The elements of Ω will be called points and be denoted generically by ω . So $\Omega = \{\omega\}$. Let \mathcal{F} is a σ -algebra, which be the collection of some subsets of Ω . Every element of \mathcal{F} be called event. Similar to the real probability definition in [1], we give the axiomatic definition of complex probability.

Definition 2.1. We define the complex probability as a set function $\mathbb{P} : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, with every event $A \in \mathcal{F}$, satisfying the following axioms:

- (1) $\mathbb{P}(A) = p + \alpha i$, $i = \sqrt{-1}$, where $p, \alpha \in \mathbb{R}$, and $0 \leq p \leq 1$, $-1 \leq \alpha \leq 1$.
- (2) If $A_n \in \mathcal{F}$ and $\{A_n\}$ are disjoint, then $\mathbb{P}(\cup_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \mathbb{P}(A_n)$;
- (3) The complex probability of the sure event is 1. Namely $\mathbb{P}(\Omega) = 1$.

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Just as the Kolmogorov axiomatics [1], the complex probability space is a triple $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$. The special case, $\alpha = 0$ for every $A \in \mathcal{F}$, of the complex probability becomes real probability, i.e., $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, Re(\mathbb{P}))$ is a real probability space. The complex probability has the following main properties.

Theorem 2.2. *Suppose $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ is a complex probability space, then*

(2.1) (1) $\mathbb{P}(\phi) = 0$, where ϕ is empty set, or impossible event;

(2) If $A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n \in \mathcal{F}$ are disjoint, then $\mathbb{P}(\cup_{k=1}^n A_k) = \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbb{P}(A_k)$;

(3) For any $A \in \mathcal{F}$, $\mathbb{P}(\bar{A}) = 1 - \mathbb{P}(A)$, where \bar{A} is the complement set of A

(4) If $A, B \in \mathcal{F}$ and $A \subseteq B$, then $\mathbb{P}(B - A) = \mathbb{P}(B) - \mathbb{P}(A)$

(5) For any $A, B \in \mathcal{F}$, then $\mathbb{P}(B - A) = \mathbb{P}(B) - \mathbb{P}(A \cap B)$.

Proof. (1) Because $\Omega, \phi, \phi, \dots$ are disjoint, then

$$(2.2) \quad 1 = \mathbb{P}(\Omega) = \mathbb{P}(\Omega \cup \phi \cup \phi \cup \dots) = \mathbb{P}(\Omega) + \mathbb{P}(\phi) + \mathbb{P}(\phi) + \dots$$

Since $\mathbb{P}(\Omega) + \mathbb{P}(\phi) + \mathbb{P}(\phi) + \dots$ is convergence, so $\mathbb{P}(\phi) = 0$.

(2) Let $A_k = \phi$, $k = n + 1, n + 2, \dots$, then

$$(2.3) \quad \mathbb{P}(\cup_{k=1}^n A_k) = \mathbb{P}(\cup_{k=1}^{\infty} A_k) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \mathbb{P}(A_k) = \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbb{P}(A_k).$$

(3) For $A \cup \bar{A} = \Omega$ and A, \bar{A} are disjoint, then

$$(2.4) \quad \mathbb{P}(\Omega) = \mathbb{P}(A \cup \bar{A}) = \mathbb{P}(A) + \mathbb{P}(\bar{A}) = 1,$$

consequently, $\mathbb{P}(\bar{A}) = 1 - \mathbb{P}(A)$.

(4) For $A \subseteq B$, then

$$A = B \cup (A - B)$$

and $B, (A - B)$ are disjoint. Using (2.3) gives

$$\mathbb{P}(B) = \mathbb{P}(A) + \mathbb{P}(B - A).$$

therefore, $\mathbb{P}(B - A) = \mathbb{P}(B) - \mathbb{P}(A)$.

(5) For $B - A = B - AB$ and $AB \subseteq B$, using property (4) gives

$$\mathbb{P}(B - A) = \mathbb{P}(B) - \mathbb{P}(A \cap B).$$

□

We remark that some properties of real probability do not hold for complex probability. For example, in real probability, if $A, B \in \mathcal{F}$ and $A \subseteq B$, then $P(A) \leq P(B)$, but this inequality does not hold for complex probability.

The following theorem gives one method to define a complex probability by three real probabilities.

Theorem 2.3. *Let P_1, P_2, P_3 be real probability measures on measurable space (Ω, \mathcal{F}) . For every $A \in \mathcal{F}$, let*

$$(2.5) \quad \mathbb{P}(A) = P_1(A) + i(P_2(A) - P_3(A)),$$

Then \mathbb{P} is a complex probability on (Ω, \mathcal{F}) .

Proof. Since

$$(2.6) \quad \mathbb{P}(A) = P_1(A) + i(P_2(A) - P_3(A)),$$

and

$$(2.7) \quad 0 \leq P_1(A) \leq 1, \quad -1 \leq P_2(A) - P_3(A) \leq 1,$$

so, the axioms (1) in the definition of complex probability holds.

If $A_n \in \mathcal{F}$ and $\{A_n\}$ are disjoint, then

$$(2.8) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(\cup_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n) &= P_1(\cup_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n) + i(P_2(\cup_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n) - P_3(\cup_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n)) \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \{P_1(A_n) + i(P_2(A_n) - P_3(A_n))\} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \mathbb{P}(A_n), \end{aligned}$$

therefore, the axioms (2) in the definition of complex probability holds.

By definition,

$$(2.9) \quad \mathbb{P}(\Omega) = P_1(\Omega) + i(P_2(\Omega) - P_3(\Omega)), = 1 + i(1 - 1) = 1,$$

the axioms (3) in the definition of complex probability holds. \square

Corollary 1. *Under the definition 2.5, for any $A, B \in \mathcal{F}$, the following addition formula of complex probability holds.*

$$(2.10) \quad \mathbb{P}(A \cup B) = \mathbb{P}(A) + \mathbb{P}(B) - \mathbb{P}(A \cap B)$$

Proof. For any real probability P on measurable space (Ω, \mathcal{F}) , then

$$(2.11) \quad P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B) - P(A \cap B),$$

consequently, by definition 2.5,

$$(2.12) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(A \cup B) &= P_1(A \cup B) + i\{P_2(A \cup B) - P_3(A \cup B)\} \\ &= P_1(A) + P_1(B) - P_1(A \cap B) + \\ &\quad i\{P_2(A) + P_2(B) - P_2(A \cap B) - (P_3(A) + P_3(B) - P_3(A \cap B))\} \\ &= P_1(A) + i(P_2(A) - P_3(A)) + P_1(B) + i(P_2(B) - P_3(B)) - \\ &\quad \{P_1(A \cap B) + i(P_2(A \cap B) - P_3(A \cap B))\} \\ &= \mathbb{P}(A) + \mathbb{P}(B) - \mathbb{P}(A \cap B), \end{aligned}$$

thus, we finish the proof. \square

In general, the following equality for complex probability hold: for any $A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n \in \mathcal{F}$, then

$$(2.13) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(A_1 \cup A_2 \cup \dots \cup A_n) &= \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbb{P}(A_i) - \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq n} \mathbb{P}(A_i \cap A_j) \\ &\quad + \sum_{1 \leq i < j < k \leq n} \mathbb{P}(A_i \cap A_j \cap A_k) + \dots + (-1)^{n-1} \mathbb{P}(A_1 \cap A_2 \cap \dots \cap A_n). \end{aligned}$$

Example 2.4. Let $\Omega = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, \mathcal{F} be the collection of all subsets of Ω . We define three real probabilities P_1, P_2, P_3 by

$$\begin{aligned} P_1\{0\} &= \frac{1}{3}, & P_1\{1\} &= \frac{1}{4}, & P_1\{2\} &= \frac{1}{4}; & P_1\{3\} &= \frac{1}{6}; \\ P_2\{0\} &= \frac{1}{4}, & P_2\{1\} &= \frac{1}{3}, & P_2\{2\} &= \frac{1}{4}; & P_2\{3\} &= \frac{1}{6}; \\ P_3\{0\} &= \frac{1}{3}, & P_3\{1\} &= \frac{1}{4}, & P_3\{2\} &= \frac{1}{6}; & P_3\{3\} &= \frac{1}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, due to the definition 2.5,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}\{0\} &= P_1\{0\} + i(P_2\{0\} - P_3\{0\}) = \frac{1}{3} + i\left(\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{3}\right) = \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{12}i, \\ \mathbb{P}\{1\} &= P_1\{1\} + i(P_2\{1\} - P_3\{1\}) = \frac{1}{4} + i\left(\frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{4}\right) = \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{12}i, \\ \mathbb{P}\{2\} &= P_1\{2\} + i(P_2\{2\} - P_3\{2\}) = \frac{1}{4} + i\left(\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{6}\right) = \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{12}i, \\ \mathbb{P}\{3\} &= P_1\{3\} + i(P_2\{3\} - P_3\{3\}) = \frac{1}{6} + i\left(\frac{1}{6} - \frac{1}{4}\right) = \frac{1}{6} - \frac{1}{12}i, \\ \mathbb{P}\{1, 2\} &= P_1\{1, 2\} + i(P_2\{1, 2\} - P_3\{1, 2\}) = \frac{1}{2} + i\left(\frac{7}{12} - \frac{5}{12}\right) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{6}i, \\ \mathbb{P}\{2, 3\} &= P_1\{2, 3\} + i(P_2\{2, 3\} - P_3\{2, 3\}) = \frac{5}{12} + i\left(\frac{5}{12} - \frac{5}{12}\right) = \frac{5}{12}, \\ \mathbb{P}\{1, 2, 3\} &= P_1\{1, 2, 3\} + i(P_2\{1, 2, 3\} - P_3\{1, 2, 3\}) = \frac{2}{3} + \frac{1}{12}i. \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to see,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}\{1, 2, 3\} &= \mathbb{P}\{1\} + \mathbb{P}\{2\} + \mathbb{P}\{3\}, \\ \mathbb{P}\{1, 2, 3\} &= 1 - \mathbb{P}\{0\}, \\ \mathbb{P}\{1, 2, 3\} &= \mathbb{P}\{\{1, 2\} \cup \{2, 3\}\} = \mathbb{P}\{\{1, 2\}\} + \mathbb{P}\{\{2, 3\}\} - \mathbb{P}\{\{1, 2\} \cap \{2, 3\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

3. CONDITIONAL COMPLEX PROBABILITY AND INDEPENDENT EVENTS

Independent events is one of the most important concepts in probability theory. In this section, we give the conditional complex probability, multiplication formula of complex probability and independent events. Using the definition 2.5, we can define the conditional complex probability $\mathbb{P}(A|B)$, which is the complex probability of an event A to occur under the condition that an event B has occurred.

Definition 3.1. Suppose $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ is a complex probability space, \mathbb{P} is defined by (2.5). For any $A, B \in \mathcal{F}$, such that $P_1(B)P_2(B)P_3(B) > 0$, the conditional complex probability defined by

$$(3.1) \quad \mathbb{P}(A|B) = P_1(A|B) + i(P_2(A|B) - P_3(A|B)).$$

Using the definition 3.1, we obtain the following multiplication formula of complex probability.

Theorem 3.2. Suppose $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ is a complex probability space, \mathbb{P} is defined by (2.5). For any $A, B \in \mathcal{F}$, such that $P_1(B) = P_2(B) = P_3(B) > 0$, then

$$(3.2) \quad \mathbb{P}(A \cap B) = \mathbb{P}(B)\mathbb{P}(A|B).$$

Proof. By definition (2.5),

$$\begin{aligned}
 (3.3) \quad \mathbb{P}(A|B) &= P_1(A|B) + i\{P_2(A|B) - P_3(A|B)\} \\
 &= \frac{P_1(A \cap B)}{P_1(B)} + i\left\{ \frac{P_2(A \cap B)}{P_2(B)} - \frac{P_3(A \cap B)}{P_3(B)} \right\} \\
 &= \frac{P_1(A \cap B) + i\{P_2(A \cap B) - P_3(A \cap B)\}}{P_1(B)} \\
 &= \frac{P_1(A \cap B) + i\{P_2(A \cap B) - P_3(A \cap B)\}}{P_1(B) + i\{P_2(B) - P_3(B)\}} = \frac{\mathbb{P}(A \cap B)}{\mathbb{P}(B)},
 \end{aligned}$$

we finish to prove (3.2). \square

Similarly, if $A, B, C \in \mathcal{F}$, such that $P_1(C) = P_2(C) = P_3(C)$, and $P_1(B \cap C) = P_2(B \cap C) = P_3(B \cap C) > 0$, then

$$(3.4) \quad \mathbb{P}(A \cap B \cap C) = \mathbb{P}(C)\mathbb{P}(B|C)\mathbb{P}(A|B \cap C).$$

We remark that (3.3) is the well known Bayes' formula. Based on the conditional probability, we define the independent events.

Definition 3.3. Suppose $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ is a complex probability space, and $A, B \in \mathcal{F}$. If

$$(3.5) \quad \mathbb{P}(A \cap B) = \mathbb{P}(A)\mathbb{P}(B),$$

then, A and B be called independent events.

Theorem 3.4. Suppose $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ is a complex probability space, \mathbb{P} is defined by (2.5). If A, B be independent events and $P_1(B) = P_2(B) = P_3(B) > 0$, then

$$(3.6) \quad \mathbb{P}(A) = \mathbb{P}(A|B).$$

Proof. Under the conditions of the theorem, then

$$(3.7) \quad \mathbb{P}(A \cap B) = \mathbb{P}(A)\mathbb{P}(B)$$

and

$$(3.8) \quad \mathbb{P}(A \cap B) = \mathbb{P}(B)\mathbb{P}(A|B),$$

therefor, (3.6) holds. \square

We also give the following sufficient condition for independent events.

Theorem 3.5. Suppose $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ is a complex probability space, \mathbb{P} is defined by (2.5). If A, B be independent events with respect to P_1, P_2, P_3 distinguishly and $P_1(B) = P_2(B) = P_3(B)$, then A, B are independent events with respect to complex probability \mathbb{P} .

Proof. Because A, B be independent events with respect to P_1, P_2, P_3 , so

$$P_1(A \cap B) = P_1(A)P_1(B),$$

$$P_2(A \cap B) = P_2(A)P_2(B),$$

$$P_3(A \cap B) = P_3(A)P_3(B).$$

Since $P_1(B) = P_2(B) = P_3(B)$, cosequently

$$\begin{aligned}
(3.9) \quad \mathbb{P}(A \cap B) &= P_1(A \cap B) + i \{P_2(A \cap B) - P_3(A \cap B)\} \\
&= P_1(A)P_1(B) + i \{P_2(A)P_2(B) - P_3(A)P_3(B)\} \\
&= P_1(B) \{P_1(A) + i[P_2(A) - P_3(A)]\} \\
&= P_1(B)\mathbb{P}(A) = \{P_1(B) + i[P_2(B) - P_3(B)]\}\mathbb{P}(A) \\
&= \mathbb{P}(B)\mathbb{P}(A),
\end{aligned}$$

A, B are independent events with respect to \mathbb{P} . \square

4. THE FORMULA OF TOTAL PROBABILITY AND THE BAYES' FORMULA

The formula of total probability and the Bayes' formula play an important role in many fields. In this section, we give the formula of total complex probability and the complex Bayes' formula.

Definition 4.1. Suppose $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ is a complex probability space, \mathbb{P} is defined by (2.5). Let $B_k \in \mathcal{F}$ are a countable family of disjoint events, such that their union is equal to Ω and $P_1(B_k)P_2(B_k)P_3(B_k) > 0, k = 1, 2, \dots$. Such a family $\{B_k\}$ is called a partition of the space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$.

Theorem 4.2. Let $\{B_k\}$ be a partition of $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$, \mathbb{P} is defined by (2.5), such that $P_1(B_k) = P_2(B_k) = P_3(B_k), k = 1, 2, \dots$. Then, for every $A \in \mathcal{F}$, the following formula of total complex probability holds

$$(4.1) \quad \mathbb{P}\{A\} = \mathbb{P}(B_1)\mathbb{P}(A|B_1) + \mathbb{P}(B_2)\mathbb{P}(A|B_2) + \dots$$

Proof. Using the definitions 4.1 and multiplication formula (3.2) gives

$$\begin{aligned}
(4.2) \quad \mathbb{P}\{A\} &= \mathbb{P}\{A \cap \Omega\} = \mathbb{P}\{A \cap B_1\} + \mathbb{P}\{A \cap B_2\} + \dots \\
&= \mathbb{P}(B_1)\mathbb{P}(A|B_1) + \mathbb{P}(B_2)\mathbb{P}(A|B_2) + \dots,
\end{aligned}$$

consequently, (4.1) holds. \square

Theorem 4.3. Let $\{B_k\}$ be a partition of $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$, \mathbb{P} is defined by (2.5), such that $P_1(B_k) = P_2(B_k) = P_3(B_k), k = 1, 2, \dots$. Then, for every $A \in \mathcal{F}$, satisfied $P_1(A) = P_2(A) = P_3(A) > 0$, the following Bayes' formula holds

$$(4.3) \quad \mathbb{P}\{B_k|A\} = \frac{\mathbb{P}(B_k)\mathbb{P}(A|B_k)}{\mathbb{P}(B_1)\mathbb{P}(A|B_1) + \mathbb{P}(B_2)\mathbb{P}(A|B_2) + \dots}, k = 1, 2, \dots$$

Proof. Using the Bayes' formula (3.3), multiplication formula (3.2) and the formula of total probability (4.1) gives

$$\begin{aligned}
(4.4) \quad \mathbb{P}\{B_k|A\} &= \frac{\mathbb{P}(A \cap B_k)}{\mathbb{P}(A)} \\
&= \frac{\mathbb{P}(B_k)\mathbb{P}(A|B_k)}{\mathbb{P}(B_1)\mathbb{P}(A|B_1) + \mathbb{P}(B_2)\mathbb{P}(A|B_2) + \dots}.
\end{aligned}$$

\square

We remark that, if both $\mathbb{P}(A)$ and $\mathbb{P}(B)$ are real numbers, $\mathbb{P}(A \cap B)$ could be complex number. For example, let

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{P}\{1\} &= \frac{1}{6} + 0.1i, & \mathbb{P}\{3\} &= \frac{1}{6} + 0.1i, & \mathbb{P}\{5\} &= \frac{1}{6} + 0.20i, \\
\mathbb{P}\{2\} &= \frac{1}{6} - 0.1i, & \mathbb{P}\{4\} &= \frac{1}{6} - 0.1i, & \mathbb{P}\{6\} &= \frac{1}{6} - 0.20i,
\end{aligned}$$

and let $A = \{1, 2\}$, $B = \{1, 4\}$, then $\mathbb{P}\{A\} = \mathbb{P}\{B\} = \frac{1}{3}$, $\mathbb{P}\{A \cap B\} = \mathbb{P}\{1\} = \frac{1}{6} + 0.1i$.

5. DISCRETE AND CONTINUOUS OF COMPLEX RANDOM VARIABLES

Let $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ be a probability space, a \mathcal{F} -measurable function X defined on Ω is called a random variable. Like real random variables, there are two common types of complex random variables: discrete type and continuous type. The definitions are given below.

Definition 5.1. Suppose X be a random variable on a complex probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$, X is called a discrete complex random variable, if $\Omega = \{x_k, k = 1, 2, \dots\}$, and

$$(5.1) \quad \mathbb{P}\{X = x_k\} = \alpha_k + i\beta_k, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots,$$

such that

$$(5.2) \quad (1) \alpha_k \geq 0, \quad -1 \leq \beta_k \leq 1; \quad (2) \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \alpha_k = 1, \quad \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \beta_k = 0, \quad \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |\beta_k| \leq 2.$$

Example 5.2. The complex uniform distribution on a sample space Ω containing n elements is the \mathbb{P} defined by

$$(5.3) \quad \mathbb{P}\{\omega_k\} = \frac{1}{n} + \beta_k i, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n,$$

for every $\omega_k \in \Omega$ and $-1 \leq \beta_k \leq 1$, $\sum_{k=1}^n \beta_k = 0$, $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |\beta_k| \leq 2$.

$$(5.4) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}\{1\} &= \frac{1}{6} + 0.1i, & \mathbb{P}\{3\} &= \frac{1}{6} + 0.15i, & \mathbb{P}\{5\} &= \frac{1}{6} + 0.20i, \\ \mathbb{P}\{2\} &= \frac{1}{6} - 0.1i, & \mathbb{P}\{4\} &= \frac{1}{6} - 0.15i, & \mathbb{P}\{6\} &= \frac{1}{6} - 0.20i, \end{aligned}$$

is one of complex uniform distribution.

Definition 5.3. Suppose X be a random variable on a complex probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$, X is called a continuous complex random variable, if there exist three real integrable functions $P_1(x), P_2(x), P_3(x)$, satisfying the following conditions

$$(5.5) \quad (1) P_1(x) \geq 0, P_2(x) \geq 0, P_3(x) \geq 0, \quad x \in \mathbb{R};$$

$$(2) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} P_i(x) dx = 1, \quad i = 1, 2, 3;$$

$$(3) \text{For any } a < b \in \mathbb{R},$$

$$\mathbb{P}(a < X \leq b) = \int_a^b P_1(x) dx + i \left(\int_a^b P_2(x) dx - \int_a^b P_3(x) dx \right).$$

If $P_2(x) = P_3(x)$ for every $x \in \mathbb{R}$, then X be a random variable on a real probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \text{Re}(\mathbb{P}))$

Definition 5.4. Let $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ is a complex probability space and X is a continuous random variable on this space. For any $\mu \in \mathbb{R}$, $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}^+$, if

$$(5.6) \quad P_1(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}},$$

we call X distributed complex normal distribution $\mathbb{N}(\mu, \sigma^2)$.

Example 5.5. If X distributed the complex normal distribution $\mathbb{N}(\mu, \sigma^2)$, then for any $a < b \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$(5.7) \quad \mathbb{P}(a < X \leq b) = \int_a^b \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} dx + i \left(\int_a^b P_2(x) dx - \int_a^b P_3(x) dx \right).$$

If $\mu = 0$, $\sigma^2 = 1$,

$$(5.8) \quad P_2(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{100}, & -50 \leq x \leq 50, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

and

$$(5.9) \quad P_3(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{20}, & -10 \leq x \leq 10, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

then

$$(5.10) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(-\infty < X \leq 0) &= \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}} dx + i \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 P_2(x) dx - \int_{-\infty}^0 P_3(x) dx \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^0 e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}} dt + i \left(\int_{-50}^0 \frac{1}{100} dx - \int_{-10}^0 \frac{1}{20} dx \right) = 0.5, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$(5.11) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(0 < X \leq 1) &= \int_0^1 \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}} dx + i \left(\int_0^1 P_2(x) dx - \int_0^1 P_3(x) dx \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_0^1 e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}} dt + i \left(\int_0^1 \frac{1}{100} dx - \int_0^1 \frac{1}{20} dx \right) = 0.3413 - 0.040i. \end{aligned}$$

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